

MORPHOLOGO – SYNTACTICAL NATURE OF VOICE

Ибраимова Гулмира

The master of Karakalpak state university

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The voice defines the relationship between the actor, the undergoer of the action and the action. This may be considered a rather mechanical relationship between the subject and the verb. A verb so-called “active” voice indicates that the subject is performing the action expressed in the verb, if on the other hand, the voice is “passive” the verb form indicates that the subject is undergoing or is being subjected to the action of the verb. In the active voice further differentiation may be indicate the transitive in which the action is carried across to an object or in transitive in which there is no object.

In addition to the active and passive voices, some languages distinguish a so-called “middle” voice, in which one does something to or for oneself. If the action is always performed by the subject and upon himself, it is called “**reflexive**” voice. If the action is formed by two or more subjects and if these subjects act upon each other, the relationship of voice generally called “reciprocal” voice.

ABSTRACT

This article examines the forms of the verb that illustrates the connection between the action and its subject, indicating if the action is done by the subject or the predicate verb.

From this point of view the category of voice presents a special linguistic interest. It is to be noted in this connection that there is nothing more supremely characteristic of English, especially in its later periods, than the extend to which it has developed the use of passive formation. The discussion of this belongs mostly to morphologo - syntactic problems.

The aim of this article is to describe and analyze the forms of the verb which shows the relation between the action and its subject indicating whether action is performed by the subject or the predicate verb.

The category, which we are going to describe and analyse, is the category that involves the relationship of subject and object in the sentence or clause.

[Oxford concise companion to the English language, p 643]

The problem of voice was learned and studied by foreign linguists **O.Jespersen, CH.Fries, Russian linguistis B .Ilyish, M. Blokh, B.Arakin,**

V.Vonogradov and by our native linguists and grammarians J. Buranov, U.Yusupova, Sh. Saparov and other linguistic scientists.

As a grammatical category voice is the form of the verb which shows the relation between the action and its subject indicating if the action is performed of the subject or passes on to it. Accordingly, there are two voices in English: the active voice and the passive voice. The active voice shows that the action is performed by its subject, that the subject is the doer of the action. The passive voice that the subject is acted upon, that is the recipient of the action. For example: I wrote a letter-active voice . A letter was written by me-passive voice

The **choice** of the passive construction is often due to the fact that the agent is unknown or the speaker prefers not to speak of him. When the active subject is unknown or can not be stated for example: The town **is** well **supplied** with water.I **was told** she had left Tashkent

When the active subject is not mentioned for some special reasons. For example: Enough has been said here of your books. You **have been told** so many times not to take these books.

When the doer of the action is expressed passive forms is generally preferred due to the greater interest taken in the " Passive" than in the " active" subject. The entire process of grammar involves selection and so it is with the distribution of the active and passive forms in English. The functional sentence perspective may depend on the choice of the active or passive form.

The passive form is often used as the effective device to make the " Psychological" subject is also grammatical subject of the sentence. This is the example

with the prepositional verb structure: The doctor **was sent** for.The bed **had not been slept** in.The child **must be taken** great care of.

The passive voice is generally expressed by analytic combinations of the auxiliary verb " **to be**" with the past participle of the notional verb.

The verb "**get**" can function in a manner very similar with " **be**". For example: My shirt got caught on a nail. He **got struck** by a stone.

The passive formed with **get** of auxiliary seems to be increasing in the frequently.

The verb "**to get**" seems closer to the true passive auxiliary to be in the following examples: She got blamed for everything. She gets teased by the other children. She gets punished regularly.

It should be noted that to get is often used in preference of the verb to be because the true passive would not be clearly distinguishable from combinations of the full predicator be participial adjective complements.

The obvious opposition in the category of voice is that between active and passive. This opposition may be identified by corresponding grammatical forms involving different categories as : mood, tense and aspect. For example: He writes – it is written. He is writing –it is being written. He wrote- it was written. He has written-it has been written.He would write –it would be written.

The analysis of the passive voice in English seems to be relevant to a number of other questions. The first question is the problem of transitivity.

Relation between verbs and their object have always been a source of linguistic interest in any language. From point of

view the grammar of the English verb presents its own difficulties.

The definition equally applicable to most cases is that the object serves to make the meaning contained in the verb more special or to limit its sphere of applicability. In ordinary analysis verbs taking without prepositional objects are generally referred to as transitive, the verbs which do not take such objects are called intransitive verbs.

It is to be noted that the prepositional object, on which the division of English verbs into transitive and intransitive is based, it depends on the lexical meaning of the verb. It is very difficult to draw right border line between the two classes and so we should reasonably speak of a transitive and intransitive use of verbs. Many verbs which are generally transitive, that is take an object, are very often used within any object. And the other verbs which are generally referred to as intransitive may be used with an object. For example: He is reading a book. He is reading fluently. He stood the box in the corner. He stood at the corner.

In some cases it is doubtful which of two chance in our examples. As a regular categorical form of the verb, the passive voice is combined in the same lexeme with

other oppositional, strong forms of the verbal categories of the tense – aspect system, that is the past, the future, the continuous, the perfect.

But it has a neutralizing effect on the category of development in the forms where the auxiliary “be” must be doubly employed as the infinitive, the present participle, the past participle so that the future continuous passive, as well as, the perfect continuous are practically not used in speech. As a result, the future continuous active has as its regular counterpart by the voice opposition future indefinite passive. For example: The police **will be keeping** the army of reporters bay- The army of reporters **will be kept** at bay by the police.

In brief we can say that the category of voice is the verb differs radically from all the other considered categories from the point of voice of its referential qualities. All the our described cases of voice forms of the verb reflect different characteristics of processes, direct and oblique (indirect), as the certain fact reality existing irrespective of the speakers perception.

The property of the category of voice shows its immediate connection with syntax, which finds expression indirect transformational relations between the active and passive constructions.

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